

Appendix

Appendix A Cross-sectional RDD Results Before 2014

This section provide RDD results for each dimensions before the reform came into force, *i.e.* in 2012 and 2013.

AppendixA.1 RDD results for farmers around 10 ha of arable land in 2012

Table A1: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2012: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	-0.112* (0.068)	-173.748* (90.071)	23.964 (64.797)
Tot.Obs	397	397	397
Eff.Obs	58	67	94
Bandwidth	2.040	2.554	3.828

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table A2: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2012: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	-0.069 (0.174)	0.080 (0.134)	-0.444 (0.338)	-0.092 (0.061)
Tot.Obs	397	396	396	397
Eff.Obs	82	60	67	58
Bandwidth	3.381	2.305	2.567	2.079

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table A3: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2012: Land Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	0.117 (0.140)	-0.016 (0.055)	-0.077 (0.445)
Tot.Obs	397	397	397
Eff.Obs	74	60	95
Bandwidth	2.934	2.207	3.843

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

AppendixA.2

RDD results for farmers around 30 ha of arable land in 2012

Table A4: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2012: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	perating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	0.056 (0.075)	81.114 (106.199)	-21.132 (75.751)
Tot.Obs	366	366	366
Eff.Obs	101	140	157
Bandwidth	2.713	3.597	4.158

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table A5: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2012: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	0.017 (0.138)	-0.236 (0.256)	-0.497 (0.331)	0.051 (0.070)
Tot.Obs	366	366	366	366
Eff.Obs	106	152	80	101
Bandwidth	2.874	3.959	2.287	2.721

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table A6: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2012: Land Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	-0.100 (0.107)	-0.058 (0.072)	0.404 (0.812)
Tot.Obs	366	366	366
Eff.Obs	109	105	106
Bandwidth	2.952	2.846	2.879

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

AppendixA.3

RDD results for farmers around 10 ha of arable land in 2013

Table A7: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	0.011 (0.094)	22.675 (170.054)	60.448 (103.352)
Tot.Obs	353	353	353
Eff.Obs	66	57	74
Bandwidth	3.079	2.779	3.618

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table A8: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	-0.157 (0.160)	0.015 (0.143)	-0.913** (0.411)	0.014 (0.086)
Tot.Obs	353	352	352	353
Eff.Obs	70	55	48	66
Bandwidth	3.305	2.529	2.030	3.107

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table A9: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013: Land Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	0.048 (0.123)	0.079 (0.075)	-1.163 (0.795)
Tot.Obs	353	353	353
Eff.Obs	77	56	55
Bandwidth	3.758	2.731	2.600

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Appendix A.4 RDD results for farmers around 30 ha of arable land in 2013

Table A10: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	0.114 (0.071)	132.014 (88.408)	186.390* (107.518)

Tot.Obs	365	365	365
Eff.Obs	114	114	119
Bandwidth	3.182	3.177	3.291

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table A11: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	-0.141 (0.188)	-0.118 (0.271)	-0.940** (0.465)	0.094 (0.069)
Tot.Obs	365	365	365	365
Eff.Obs	95	113	60	121
Bandwidth	2.778	3.101	1.890	3.350

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table A12: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013: Land Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	-0.048 (0.111)	-0.079 (0.071)	-0.141 (0.730)
Tot.Obs	365	365	365
Eff.Obs	89	85	92
Bandwidth	2.566	2.500	2.638

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

AppendixB Robustness Results

Here, we presents results for different type of robustness. [AppendixB.1](#) and [AppendixB.2](#) provide, respectively, results for farmers around 10 ha and 30 ha when we adopt uniform bandwidth (6 ha, 8 ha and 10 ha) for all our estimations. [AppendixB.3](#) presents findings when we compute our main bandwidths with the estimator of [Imbens and Kalyanaraman \(2012\)](#).

AppendixB.1 Robustness for Farmers around 10 ha with different fixed-bandwidths • Bandwidth of 6 ha of arable land

Table B13: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 6: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	-0.000 (0.000)	4.946 (25.129)	-0.647 (26.500)
Total.obs	430	430	430

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B14: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 6: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	0.038* (0.021)	-0.003 (0.057)	-0.025 (0.085)	-0.001 (0.001)
Total.obs	430	430	430	430

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B15: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 6: Land

Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	-0.070** (0.035)	-0.053* (0.027)	0.174 (0.165)
Total.obs	430	430	430

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

• **Bandwidth of 8 ha of arable land**

Table B16: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 8: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	-0.001 (0.000)	-0.590 (29.513)	5.618 (28.969)
Total.obs	334	334	334

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B17: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 8: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	0.047** (0.024)	0.021 (0.062)	-0.049 (0.097)	-0.001 (0.001)
Total.obs	334	334	334	334

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B18: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 8: Land

Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	-0.071** (0.036)	-0.057** (0.024)	0.155 (0.153)
Total.obs	334	334	334

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

• **Bandwidth of 10 ha of arable land**

Table B19: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	-0.000 (0.000)	16.791 (23.778)	9.097 (25.691)
Total.obs	524	524	524

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B20: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
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	0.034*	-0.023	-0.047	-0.001
LATE	(0.020)	(0.051)	(0.074)	(0.001)
Total.obs	524	524	524	524

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

TableB21: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Land Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	-0.076** (0.032)	-0.049** (0.024)	0.231 (0.149)
Total.obs	524	524	524

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

AppendixB.2 Robustness for Farmers around 30 ha with different fixed-bandwidths • Bandwidth of 6 ha of arable land

Table B22: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 6: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	-0.000 (0.000)	-21.616 (41.124)	-21.989 (39.354)
Total.obs	548	548	548

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B23: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 6: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	0.046 (0.045)	-0.058 (0.064)	-0.020 (0.081)	-0.000 (0.001)
Total.obs	548	548	548	548

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B24: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 6: Land Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	0.003 (0.016)	-0.013 (0.013)	0.276** (0.134)
Total.obs	548	548	548

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

• **Bandwidth of 8 ha of arable land**

Table B25: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 8: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	-0.000 (0.000)	-20.735 (36.748)	-13.417 (35.925)
Total.obs	718	718	718

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B26: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 8: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	0.038 (0.039)	-0.066 (0.059)	-0.015 (0.066)	-0.000 (0.001)
Total.obs	718	718	718	718

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B27: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 8: Land Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	0.006 (0.014)	-0.014 (0.013)	0.257* (0.136)

Total.obs	718	718	718
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Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$ ** $p < 0.05$ *** $p < 0.01$. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Bandwidth of 10 ha of arable land

Table B28: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	-0.000 (0.000)	-21.843 (29.757)	-13.301 (29.104)
Total.obs	941	941	941

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Table B29: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	0.035 (0.033)	-0.054 (0.048)	-0.213 (0.173)	0.000 (0.001)
Total.obs	941	941	941	941

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

TableB30: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Land

Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	0.007 (0.014)	-0.018 (0.012)	0.216* (0.119)
Total.obs	941	941	941

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

Appendix B.3 Robustness with bandwidth *à la* Imbens and Kalyanaraman (2012) • Farmers around 10 ha of arable land

Table B31, Table B32 and Table B33 present results for the economic, environmental and land-use conditions for farmers around 10 ha with bandwidth *à la* Imbens and Kalyanaraman (2012).

Table B31: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	-0.000 (0.000)	26.237 (18.912)	30.256 (18.826)
Total.obs	964	1000	780
Opt. Band	9.060	9.549	7.459

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01.

Table B32: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	0.024 (0.016)	0.038 (0.046)	-0.012 (0.063)	-0.001 (0.001)
Total.obs	814	951	793	942
Opt. Band	7.792	8.878	7.574	8.769

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01.

Table B33: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Land Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	-0.066** (0.033)	-0.054* (0.028)	0.231 (0.149)
Total.obs	474	438	525
Opt. Band	4.706	4.164	5.077

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01.

Farmers around 30 ha of arable land

Table B34, Table B35 and Table B36 highlight finding for farmers around 30 ha related to robustness of our main results using bandwidth as suggested by Imbens and Kalyanaraman (2012).

Table B34: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Economic

	Technical Efficiency	Operating Surplus	Income before tax
LATE	-0.000 (0.000)	3.905 (24.656)	-0.471 (25.362)
Total.obs	911	1418	1225
Opt. Band	4.947	7.857	6.588

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01.

Table B35: RDD estimate for farmers around 30 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Environment

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency
LATE	0.038 (0.037)	0.035 (0.048)	-0.205 (0.169)	-0.000 (0.001)
Total.obs	743	1424	1000	911
Opt. Band	4.151	7.937	5.273	4.946

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01.

Table B36: RDD estimate for farmers around 10 ha in 2013 with a bandwidth of 10: Land Use

	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATE	0.002 (0.016)	-0.015 (0.013)	0.223* (0.119)
Total.obs	602	819	917
Opt. Band	3.306	4.484	4.971

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01.

AppendixB.4 Robustness with different thresholds

• **Difference in Discontinuity Results for 35 ha as a thresholds**

Table B37: Results for 35 ha as a thresholds

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency	Technical Efficiency	Gross Margins per non-workers	Revenue before tax per non-workers	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATT	-0.012 (0.027)	-0.067 (0.049)	0.076 (0.059)	0.001 (0.001)	0.000 (0.000)	-10.809 (34.032)	9.501 (31.922)	-0.006 (0.014)	0.000 (0.011)	-0.026 (0.122)
Total.obs	642	886	791	532	523	572	650	418	549	502
Opt. Band	3.138	4.423	3.879	2.552	2.498	2.786	3.176	1.970	2.673	2.361

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

• **Difference in Discontinuity Results fo**

45 ha as a thresholds

Table B38: Results for 45 ha as a thresholds

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency	Technical Efficiency	Gross Margins per non-workers	Revenue before tax per non-workers	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
LATT	-0.010 (0.022)	-0.050 (0.077)	-0.015 (0.086)	0.000 (0.001)	0.000 (0.000)	13.045 (29.795)	3.461 (31.829)	-0.016* (0.010)	0.003 (0.013)	0.059 (0.103)
Total.obs	594	839	629	587	592	719	757	885	615	603
Opt. Band	2.673	3.697	2.838	2.625	2.659	3.270	3.415	3.936	2.798	2.716

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01. The optimal bandwidth in the table are bandwidth for one side.

AppendixB.5 Parallel Trends for farmers around 10 ha and 30 ha

• **Parallel Trends for farmers around 10 ha**

Table B39: Parallel Trends around 10 ha

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency	Technical Efficiency	Gross Margins per non-workers	Revenue before tax per non-workers	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
TREAT	0.087** (0.039)	0.052 (0.059)	0.085 (0.072)	-0.001 (0.001)	0.000 (0.000)	-3.512 (39.506)	-2.776 (34.405)	-0.133 (0.150)	0.063 (0.117)	1.297*** (0.298)
N	743	741	741	743	743	743	743	743	743	743

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01.

• **Parallel Trends**

for farmers around 30 ha

Table B40: Parallel Trends around 30 ha

	Shannon Index	Crop protection Index	Fertilizer Index	Environmental Efficiency	Technical Efficiency	Gross Margins per non-workers	Revenue before tax per non-workers	Main crop share	Two Main crop share	Number of crops
TREAT	-0.021 (0.070)	-0.000 (0.083)	-0.098 (0.066)	-0.000 (0.001)	-0.000 (0.000)	-102.403* (60.978)	-84.518 (58.698)	0.013 (0.028)	-0.013 (0.020)	0.166 (0.255)
N	733	733	733	733	733	733	733	733	733	733

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01.

AppendixC Additional Graphs

Figure C1: Manipulation test around 10 ha of arable land in 2015

Figure C2: Manipulation test around 30 ha of arable land in 2015

Figure C3: Density of TE around before and after the reform for farmers around 10 ha and 30 ha. Vertical lines represent the mean. *Source:* Author's own computation.

Figure C4: Density of EE around before and after the reform for farmers around 10 ha and 30 ha. Vertical lines represent the mean. *Source:* Author's own computation.

AppendixD Additional Descriptive Statistics

Table D41: Descriptive Statistics around 10 ha and 30 ha of arable land

Around 10 ha						
	Below 10 ha			Above 10 ha		
	N	mean	sd	N	mean	sd
Shannon Index	1109	0.04	0.15	1462	0.35	0.33
Crop protection Index	1103	0.18	0.58	1462	0.75	0.98
Fertilizer Index	1103	0.47	0.58	1462	1	0.88
Environmental Efficiency	1109	0.69	0.16	1462	0.68	0.13
Technical Efficiency	1109	0.65	0.18	1462	0.65	0.14
Operating Surplus	1109	399.87	202.58	1462	407.72	258.65
Revenue before tax per non-workers	1109	195.88	179.13	1462	164.33	197.36
Main crop share	1109	0.28	0.41	1462	0.61	0.21
Two Main crop share	1109	0.33	0.46	1462	0.85	0.16
Number of crops	1109	0.55	0.89	1462	2.91	1.36
1st pillar subsidies	1109	17432.34	10612.77	1462	17073.5	9620.75
Green payment	424	2171.58	1289.38	573	1878.48	1147.67

Around 30 ha						
	Below 30 ha			Above 30 ha		
	N	mean	sd	N	mean	sd
Shannon Index	1462	0.35	0.33	1008	0.5	0.34
Crop protection Index	1462	0.75	0.98	1008	0.94	0.91
Fertilizer Index	1462	1	0.88	1008	1.13	0.68
Environmental Efficiency	1462	0.68	0.13	1008	0.67	0.14
Technical Efficiency	1462	0.65	0.14	1008	0.64	0.14
Operating Surplus	1462	407.72	258.65	1008	395.84	276.51
Revenue before tax per non-workers	1462	164.33	197.36	1008	151.04	218.44
Main crop share	1462	0.61	0.21	1008	0.58	0.2
Two Main crop share	1462	0.85	0.16	1008	0.81	0.16
Number of crops	1462	2.91	1.36	1008	3.52	1.46
1st pillar subsidies	1462	17073.5	9620.75	1008	16979.63	8310.78
Green payment	573	1878.48	1147.67	407	1894.24	963.65